

Transverse Fluid Flow Around a Cylinder

Jose M. Larrain*
Potomac, Maryland, U.S.A.
September 2021

Summary

The steady transverse laminar flow of a fluid around a solid circular cylinder was investigated theoretically with the Navier-Stokes equations. Instead of the infinite fluid assumed in the classical studies, a series solution was successfully developed for a fluid having a uniform velocity at a fixed distance from the cylinder.

The solution is complete, allowing the calculation of all properties of interest within the bounds of its physical assumptions and the limitations of the series method. When extrapolated to an infinite fluid it provides insight into the apparent paradoxes that have been encountered by researchers. In particular, the drag coefficient is predicted to be vanishingly small for a truly infinite fluid. The series solution does not converge at high flow velocities, at Reynolds numbers where a wake has been observed experimentally. It provides though the prediction of the absence of a wake at sufficiently low Reynolds numbers.

1. Physical Model

Instead of an infinite fluid, a physically realizable situation was adopted. It assumes a stationary solid circular cylinder of infinite length is submerged in fluid that moves perpendicular to its axis with a uniform velocity at all the points on an imaginary cylindrical surface concentric with the solid cylinder. The fluid not on the imaginary cylindrical surface is unconstrained. Figure 1 depicts on a cross-section of the cylinder the model and the coordinate system used.

Fig. 1. Coordinate system [1] and physical model.

* JOSE MIGUEL LARRAIN, M.S., D.ENG.SC. No current affiliation. Email jose.larrain@aol.com

The coordinate system and notation are identical to those of Bird, Stewart and Lightfoot [1] in their description of the classical problem. Cylindrical coordinates r, θ, z are used, with Cartesian coordinates x, y also depicted for reference. The z axis is perpendicular to the plane of the figure and coincides with the cylinder axis.

The solid cylinder of radius R is surrounded by a Newtonian fluid of constant density ρ and viscosity μ . Concentric with the cylinder there is an imaginary cylindrical surface of radius A such that the fluid at every point on this imaginary cylindrical surface has a uniform velocity V in the direction of the coordinate axis x . There are no dependencies on z or time, and there are no other constraints on the fluid.

The method and procedures used are analogous to this author's recent exposition on the motion of fluid around a sphere [2]. The basic treatments are identical: a sensible physical model and reasonable boundary conditions that allow a series solution. These two reports present many similarities in presentation as will be apparent.

1.1. Relationships

With the formulation of Bird, Stewart and Lightfoot [1], the fluid behavior is described by the stream function ψ and the following relationships, taken directly from that work:

$$v_r = -\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \theta} \quad (1)$$

$$v_\theta = +\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial r} \quad (2)$$

$$v \nabla^4 \psi = \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial (\psi, \nabla^2 \psi)}{\partial (r, \theta)} \quad (3)$$

where

$$v = \frac{\mu}{\rho} \quad (4a)$$

$$\nabla^2 = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2} \quad (4b)$$

$$\nabla^4 \psi = \nabla^2 (\nabla^2 \psi) \quad (4c)$$

$$\frac{\partial (f, g)}{\partial (x, y)} = \begin{vmatrix} \partial f / \partial x & \partial f / \partial y \\ \partial g / \partial x & \partial g / \partial y \end{vmatrix} \quad (4d)$$

1.2. Boundary Conditions

There are four boundary conditions to be satisfied:

1. The cylinder is solid and the fluid does not permeate it:

$$v_r = 0 \text{ at } r = R, \text{ or the equivalent } \psi = C_1, \text{ a constant, at } r = R \quad (5a)$$

2. No slip of the fluid at the cylinder surface

$$v_\theta = 0 \text{ at } r = R, \text{ or the equivalent } \partial \psi / \partial r = 0 \text{ at } r = R \quad (5b)$$

3, 4. At the imaginary cylinder the velocity equals V and is in the direction of the x -axis ($\theta = 0$):

$$v_r = V \cos\theta, \text{ which integrates into } \psi = -VA \sin\theta + C_2, \text{ a constant, at } r = A \quad (5c)$$

$$v_\theta = \partial\psi/\partial r = -V \sin\theta \text{ at } r = A \quad (5d)$$

2. Series Solution

Equation 3 can be arranged with the Reynolds number at the right hand side, multiplying the higher order terms of the stream function as in:

$$\nabla^4\psi = \left(\frac{\text{Re}}{2}\right) \times (\text{terms of order } \psi^2) \quad (6)$$

where the one-half fraction is used for convenience, and:

$$\frac{\text{Re}}{2} = \frac{RV\rho}{\mu} \quad (7)$$

The series solution centers on the expansion of the stream function in a power series of the form

$$\psi = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \psi_k \left(\frac{\text{Re}}{2}\right)^k \quad (8)$$

The first term, ψ_0 , would correspond to the creeping flow situation, and would be obtained from the equation:

$$\nabla^4\psi_0 = 0 \quad (9)$$

Subsequent terms, for progressively higher powers of $(\text{Re}/2)$, would be obtained in a similar fashion from those already found, as in:

$$\nabla^4\psi_k = \sum_{k_1=0}^{k-1} (\text{terms with } \psi_{k_1} \times \psi_{k-1-k_1}) \quad \text{for } k > 0 \quad (10)$$

A framework was devised that would allow the solution of these equations. Inspection of Eq. 3 reveals that a viable form for the stream function is:

$$\psi = VR \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^{n_L(k)} \sum_{j=0}^{j_L(k,n)} \sum_{i_F(k,n,j)}^{i_L(k,n,j)} b_{knji} \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^i \left(\ln\frac{r}{R}\right)^j \cos^n\theta \sin\theta \left(\frac{\text{Re}}{2}\right)^k \quad (11)$$

where b_{knji} represent dimensionless constants that would depend on geometry. For consistency with having the stream function be zero along the plane $y = 0$, integration constants C_1 and C_2 of Eqs. 5 are set as zero. The included summation limits are from insights gained during development: For each k there is a finite number of powers of $\cos\theta$. For each pair of k and n , j remains finite; and i has positive and negative values for all combinations of k , n , and j .

2.1. Procedure

Central to the procedure used is the behavior of the ∇^4 operator with the typical term of the series. When applied, the power of (r/R) is uniformly decreased by 4, while the highest powers of $\ln(r/R)$ and $\cos \theta$ are maintained:

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla^4 \left\{ \left(\frac{r}{R} \right)^i \left(\ln \frac{r}{R} \right)^j \cos^n \theta \sin \theta \right\} \\ = \left(\frac{r}{R} \right)^{i-4} \sin \theta \left\{ (i-n-1)(i-n-3)(i+n+1)(i+n-1) \left(\ln \frac{r}{R} \right)^j \cos^n \theta \right. \\ \left. + j \left(\ln \frac{r}{R} \right)^{j-1} \cos^n \theta \dots + \dots \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

It is evident that for each power of $\cos \theta$ there are four special powers of (r/R) for which their contribution to the ∇^4 operator vanishes at any desired power of $\ln(r/R)$. These are:

$$i = n + 3; n + 1; -n + 1; -n - 1 \quad (13)$$

The coefficients associated with these powers of (r/R) serve to satisfy the boundary conditions. Note also that when $n = 0$ there is $i = 1$ as a double root which requires a special procedure as described below.

When calculating a stream function component ψ_k from its ∇^4 expansion with the already-known lower order terms as in Eq. 10, we start from the highest power of $\cos \theta$ downwards, and find all coefficients for each power n in order. For a particular n we treat each power " $i - 4$," from the highest power j downwards. The corresponding coefficient b_{knji} can be calculated directly by dividing the term at the right hand side of Eq. 10 by the first factor in expansion 12. This fails however when i is one of the special values in Eq. 13, as a term at the right hand side of Eq. 10 cannot be produced by the first element in Eq. 12. That term is instead generated by the second element of a term with the next higher power of $\ln(r/R)$, i.e., $j + 1$, and is used to obtain the coefficient corresponding to that higher power.

The equation is then adjusted by including all the terms derived from the newly-found coefficients and the process repeated for lower powers of $\ln(r/R)$ until $j = 0$ (or $j=1$ for a special i) is reached for all the powers of (r/R) of the particular n . Only four coefficients are not known, corresponding to $j = 0$ and the four special powers of i in Eq. 13, and are obtained from the linear equations that result from the four boundary conditions applying to each pair of k and n :

From Eq. 5a:

$$\sum_i b_{k,n,j=0,i} = 0 \quad (14a)$$

From Eq. 5b:

$$\sum_i (i b_{k,n,j=0,i} + b_{k,n,j=1,i}) = 0 \quad (14b)$$

From Eq. 5c:

$$\sum_j \sum_i b_{k,n,j,i} \left(\frac{A}{R} \right)^i \left(\ln \frac{A}{R} \right)^j = \begin{cases} -\frac{A}{R} & \text{for } k = 0 \\ 0 & \text{for } k \geq 1 \end{cases} \quad (14c)$$

From Eq. 5d:

$$\sum_j \sum_i b_{k,n,j,i} \left(\frac{A}{R} \right)^{i-1} \left[i \left(\ln \frac{A}{R} \right)^j + j \left(\ln \frac{A}{R} \right)^{j-1} \right] = \begin{cases} -1 & \text{for } k = 0 \\ 0 & \text{for } k \geq 1 \end{cases} \quad (14d)$$

Compensation for the newly found coefficients allow continuation of the calculations with Eq. 10 to progressively lower powers of $\cos \theta$ until all terms are accounted for. When $n = 0$ and the factors with $i = 1$ are being calculated, the coefficients of the highest *two* powers of $\ln(r/R)$ in the $\nabla^4 \psi_k$ expansion are zero, and an extra higher power of $\ln(r/R)$, i.e., $j + 2$, is used to compensate for any term encountered.

3. Results

3.1. Creeping Flow

Eq. 9 describes the first term of the stream function series expansion, which is satisfied by $n = 0$ and the four elements r^3 , r , $r \ln r$, and r^{-1} .

It should be mentioned that these terms have been associated previously with creeping flow with the cylinder [e.g., 3, 4, 5], but the emphasis has been placed on discarding the highest orders (r^3 and $r \ln r$) or limiting their use to only short distances from the cylinder. This is because of the view that the highest order in any solution to the classical problem should be r^1 to have uniform flow at infinity. The intent here is to simply carry the series solution to completion.

The corresponding four coefficients satisfy the following:

From Eq. 14a:

$$b_{000,3} + b_{000,1} + 0 \times b_{00,1,1} + b_{000,-1} = 0 \quad (15a)$$

From Eq. 14b:

$$3 b_{000,4} + b_{000,1} + b_{00,1,1} - b_{000,-1} = 0 \quad (15b)$$

From Eq. 14c:

$$b_{000,3} \alpha^3 + b_{000,1} \alpha^1 + b_{00,1,1} \alpha^1 \ln \alpha + b_{000,-1} \alpha^{-1} = -\alpha \quad (15c)$$

From Eq. 14d:

$$3 b_{000,3} \alpha^3 + b_{000,1} \alpha^1 + b_{00,1,1} (\ln \alpha + 1) - b_{000,-1} \alpha^{-2} = -1 \quad (15d)$$

where

$$\alpha = \frac{A}{R} \quad (16)$$

Solution of these linear equations yields the creeping flow stream function as:

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_0 = \frac{VR}{\Delta_0} \left[\frac{1}{2} (1 + \alpha^{-1}) \alpha^{-2} \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^3 + \frac{1}{2} (1 - \alpha^{-1}) (1 + 2 \alpha^{-1} + \alpha^{-2}) \left(\frac{r}{R}\right) \right. \\ \left. - (1 + \alpha^{-1} + \alpha^{-2} + \alpha^{-3}) \left(\frac{r}{R}\right) \ln \frac{r}{R} - \frac{1}{2} (1 + \alpha^{-1}) \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^{-1} \right] \sin \theta \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

where

$$\alpha = \frac{A}{R} \quad (16)$$

$$\Delta_0 = (1 + \alpha^{-1} + \alpha^{-2} + \alpha^{-3}) \ln \alpha - (1 - \alpha^{-1}) (1 + 2 \alpha^{-1} + \alpha^{-2}) \quad (18)$$

It should be noted that as A increases towards infinity, and as long as the coordinate r remains smaller than A , this solution remains at most of the order of r^1 . In addition, this creeping flow solution, Eq. 17, yields with Eq. 1 a radial velocity with the following characteristics at the downstream stagnation point:

$$v_r = \frac{\partial v_r}{\partial r} = 0 ; \quad \frac{\partial^2 v_r}{\partial r^2} > 0 \quad \text{at } r = R; \theta = 0 \quad (19)$$

The implication is that next to the downstream side of the cylinder the radial velocity is positive at least for a small distance, irrespective of the Reynolds number (the other terms of the series). As the presence of a wake would imply a reversal of the flow in this vicinity, towards the cylinder instead, it is concluded that the present relations predict no wake behind the cylinder at sufficiently small velocities.

3.1.1. Streamlines

Figures 2 through 6 show calculated streamlines for creeping flow with various geometries, drawn on a plane perpendicular to the cylinder axis. Fluid flows from left to right, and because of symmetry the upstream and downstream lines mirror each other. The graph scales are units of R and only the region inside the imaginary cylinder is shown, with expanded detail close to the solid.

Fig. 2. Streamlines, creeping flow, $A = 2 R$

Fig. 3. Streamlines, creeping flow, $A = 4 R$

Fig. 4. Streamlines, creeping flow, $A = 10 R$

Fig. 5. Streamlines, creeping flow, $A = 100 R$

Fig. 6. Streamlines, creeping flow, $A = 1000 R$

It should be noted that the solid cylinder affects the fluid for a considerable distance. In Fig. 6 the imaginary cylinder is 1000 times wider than the solid cylinder, and streamlines are visibly curved at distances of 600 radii from the solid.

3.2. Higher Order Terms

Manual calculation is tedious and error prone, and the solution was extended by programming a digital computer to perform the required arithmetic operations and keep track of the numerous results, similar to previous series solutions of the Navier Stokes equations by the author [6, 2].

A previous contribution [6] carried throughout the calculations a geometric parameter of the flow (degree of curvature of a coiled pipe), and arrived at a general formula for the flow characteristics that included the parameter as a variable. Because of the complexity of the expressions encountered in the present work, its geometric parameter A/R was incorporated only numerically in the computations, directly at the start in boundary conditions 14c and 14d. The final results are sets of coefficients for Eq. 11 for any given value of this parameter.

Computational facilities used for the calculations reported include a personal computer with Microsoft Windows 10 running the 64-bit version of the gfortran Fortran compiler [7] together with the extended precision package MPFUN2020 [8] configured for 400 digits of precision. The latter was found necessary to minimize rounding-off errors in the many operations with numbers of widely varying magnitude.

More than 5,000 non-zero coefficients were computed for each A/R in the series solution for the stream function to the twelfth power of the Reynolds number. Table 1 presents overall statistics. As noted in the table, even powers of the Reynolds number are associated with only even powers of $\cos \theta$ and only odd powers of the coordinate r . Odd powers of the Reynolds number are associated with only odd powers of $\cos \theta$ and even powers of r .

Table 1. Statistics of the Series Solution for the Stream Function

Power of Re	Highest power of $\cos \theta$	Highest power of $\ln (r/R)$	Powers of (r/R)		
			Type	Highest	Lowest
0	0	1	Odd	3	-1
1	1(odds)	2	Even	6	-2
2	2(evens)	3	Odd	9	-3
3	3(odds)	4	Even	12	-4
4	4(evens)	5	Odd	15	-5
5	5(odds)	6	Even	18	-6
6	6(evens)	7	Odd	21	-7
7	7(odds)	8	Even	24	-8
8	8(evens)	9	Odd	27	-9
9	9(odds)	10	Even	30	-10
10	10(evens)	11	Odd	33	-11
11	11(odds)	12	Even	36	-12
12	12(evens)	13	Odd	39	-13

Table 2 presents a limited sampling of the results, the coefficients for the stream function for A/R from 2 to 1000, for powers of $(Re/2)$ up to 2. For clarity and compactness, figures are shown in Fortran's exponential format, rounded to four significant digits.

Table 2. Coefficients b_{knj} for the Stream Function, Eq. 11

$A/R=2$			$i = \text{Power of } r/R$												
k	n	j	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	0	-1	-2	-3
0	0	0							1.074E+00		3.221E+00		-4.294E+00		
0	0	1									-1.074E+01				
1	1	0				4.802E-02		7.343E+00		-1.138E+01		4.036E+00		-5.123E-02	
1	1	1						-3.842E+00		-3.170E+00					
1	1	2								-1.441E+01					
2	0	0	-1.289E-03	-2.870E-01			-1.826E+01		3.483E+01		-5.149E+00		-1.112E+01		-1.014E-02
2	0	1		1.547E-01			1.570E+01		-1.657E+00		-2.710E+01		-4.264E+00		
2	0	2					-3.222E+00		2.848E+01		9.747E+00				
2	0	3							-6.445E+00		-1.031E+01				
2	2	0	1.719E-03	8.798E-01			3.945E+01		-2.635E+01		-1.382E+01		-2.088E-01		4.054E-02
2	2	1		-3.609E-01			-2.165E+01		-8.400E+01		-4.635E+00				
2	2	2							-2.191E+01						
2	2	3							-2.578E+01						
$A/R=4$															
0	0	0							5.836E-02		8.755E-01		-9.338E-01		
0	0	1									-1.984E+00				
1	1	0				1.419E-04		1.063E-01		-1.111E-01		-1.447E-01		1.494E-01	
1	1	1						-3.860E-02		1.337E-01					
1	1	2								-4.922E-01					
2	0	0	-2.071E-07	-2.246E-04			-5.859E-02		1.867E-01		-8.487E-02		-4.048E-02		-2.532E-03
2	0	1		8.449E-05			3.910E-02		-1.263E-01		-1.384E-01		-3.271E-03		
2	0	2					-5.985E-03		2.099E-01		5.277E-02				
2	0	3							-4.070E-02		-7.661E-02				
2	2	0	2.761E-07	6.662E-04			1.456E-01		-3.087E-02		-6.121E-02		-6.435E-02		1.013E-02
2	2	1		-1.971E-04			-5.881E-02		-3.673E-01		-1.867E-01				
2	2	2							-6.942E-02						
2	2	3							-1.628E-01						
$A/R=10$															
0	0	0							3.744E-03		3.706E-01		-3.744E-01		
0	0	1									-7.562E-01				
1	1	0				5.839E-07		3.983E-03		1.190E-01		-2.659E-01		1.429E-01	
1	1	1						-9.436E-04		3.292E-02					
1	1	2								-7.148E-02					
2	0	0	-5.465E-11	-5.362E-07			-1.075E-03		1.615E-02		3.430E-02		-4.746E-02		-1.907E-03

Table 2 (cont'd)

k	n	j	$i \rightarrow 9$	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	0	-1	-2	-3
2	0	1			1.325E-07		5.274E-04		-1.367E-02		-1.288E-01		1.137E-02		
2	0	2					-5.575E-05		1.225E-02		-1.871E-02				
2	0	3							-2.252E-03		-4.460E-03				
2	2	0	7.287E-11		1.561E-06		3.192E-03		9.369E-03		8.325E-03		-2.851E-02		7.626E-03
2	2	1			-3.091E-07		-9.216E-04		-1.552E-04		-5.696E-02				
2	2	2							-2.520E-03						
2	2	3							-9.009E-03						

 $A/R=100$

0	0	0							1.387E-05		1.387E-01		-1.387E-01		
0	0	1									-2.774E-01				
1	1	0				8.012E-12		1.057E-05		1.344E-01		-2.712E-01		1.368E-01	
1	1	1						-1.282E-06		4.804E-03					
1	1	2								-9.616E-03					
2	0	0	-2.778E-18		-5.233E-12		-1.710E-06		1.003E-02		2.174E+00		-2.183E+00		-1.436E-03
2	0	1			6.667E-13		4.863E-07		-2.063E-03		-4.394E+00		4.658E-03		
2	0	2					-2.778E-08		6.112E-04		-9.069E-03				
2	0	3							-1.111E-04		-2.222E-04				
2	2	0	3.703E-18		1.501E-11		6.110E-06		3.987E-03		4.532E-03		-1.427E-02		5.744E-03
2	2	1			-1.556E-12		-9.939E-07		5.577E-03		-1.914E-02				
2	2	2							-1.113E-04						
2	2	3							-4.445E-04						

 $A/R=1000$

0	0	0							8.463E-08		8.463E-02		-8.463E-02		
0	0	1									-1.693E-01				
1	1	0				2.985E-16		5.862E-08		1.326E-01		-2.661E-01		1.335E-01	
1	1	1						-4.775E-09		1.791E-03					
1	1	2								-3.581E-03					
2	0	0	-6.315E-25		-1.767E-16		-8.101E-09		1.019E-02		9.323E+01		-9.324E+01		-1.004E-03
2	0	1			1.516E-17		1.615E-09		-1.051E-03		-1.865E+02		2.806E-03		
2	0	2					-6.315E-11		1.389E-04		-5.554E-03				
2	0	3							-2.526E-05		-5.052E-05				
2	2	0	8.420E-25		5.041E-16		3.089E-08		2.555E-03		2.777E-03		-9.349E-03		4.017E-03
2	2	1			-3.536E-17		-3.481E-09		3.598E-03		-1.134E-02				
2	2	2							-2.526E-05						
2	2	3							-1.010E-04						

3.2.1. Convergence

This series solution for the stream function does not converge at high Reynolds numbers. At low fluid velocities the terms involving high powers of the Reynolds number are small and do not affect the overall values: the series converges at all locations. At high Reynolds numbers the higher order terms can become significant and because of varying signs the series does not converge.

Convergence was assessed at a given fluid velocity by calculating the stream function for increasing powers of the Reynolds number and observing the behavior at the highest powers at various locations. Little variation in going from one power of the Reynolds number to a higher power was taken as indicative of convergence. All calculations mentioned were made with up to the twelfth power of the Reynolds number.

3.2.2. Streamlines

Figures 7 through 11 show streamlines for various geometries, calculated for fluid velocities for which the series appears to converge, from observations with the series expansion up to the twelfth power of the Reynolds number.

Fig. 7. Streamlines, $A = 2R$, $Re = 10$, near convergence limit.

Fig. 8. Streamlines, $A = 4R$, $Re = 4.4$, near convergence limit.

Fig. 9. Streamlines, $A = 10 R$, $Re = 1.6$, near convergence limit.

Fig. 10. Streamlines, $A = 100 R$, $Re = 0.12$, near convergence limit.

Fig. 11. Streamlines, $A = 1000 R$, $Re = 0.016$, near convergence limit.

3.3. Discussion

At low Reynolds numbers the stream function is close to the creeping flow solution, which has streamlines symmetric about the plane with $x = 0$. At higher flow velocities the streamlines are no longer symmetric, with the downstream paths being further away from the solid cylinder than the upstream ones, as shown in figures 7 to 11. The effect seems to hint at flow separation downstream, indicative of a wake, but it appears that this solution does not converge at the higher Reynolds numbers where this would take place. No clear insights are provided about wake development or structure.

Within its region of convergence, the series solution presented here appears comprehensive and able to provide all the properties of the flow. The assumed physical model, with the imaginary fluid source, allowed for a realistic set of boundary conditions that translated into the necessary and sufficient relationships required for a complete solution. No limitations are apparent in the assumed physical model, even when extrapolated to the classic problem of an infinite fluid with uniform flow at infinity.

Derived properties are presented in what follows along with inferences and conjectures about the paradoxes associated with this situation.

4. Pressure

The equation of motion [1] allows the calculation of the pressure within the fluid in terms of velocity gradients that can be obtained from the stream function. For the present situation there are two equations providing separately the partial derivatives of the pressure with respect to r and with respect to θ . Integration produces the pressure after reconciliation of the various integration constants from both equations. Details are in Bird, Stewart and Lightfoot [1].

With the stream function as the power series of Eq. 11, the pressure compensated for the hydrostatic head (modified pressure) becomes a power series in (r/R) , $\ln(r/R)$, $\cos \theta$, and the Reynolds number:

$$\mathcal{P} = p + \rho gh = \frac{\mu V}{R} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^{n_L(k)} \sum_{j=0}^{j_L(k,n)} \sum_{i_F(k,n,j)}^{i_L(k,n,j)} p_{knji} \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^i \left(\ln\frac{r}{R}\right)^j \cos^n \theta \left(\frac{Re}{2}\right)^k \quad (20)$$

where p_{knji} represent dimensionless constants and n_L, j_L, i_F, i_L represent finite limits.

4.1. Results

4.1.1. Creeping Flow

Eq. 17 and the equation of motion provide after integration the pressure field for creeping flow:

$$\mathcal{P}_0 = -\frac{2\mu V}{R\Delta_0} \left[2(1 + \alpha^{-1})\alpha^{-2} \left(\frac{r}{R}\right) + (1 + \alpha^{-1} + \alpha^{-2} + \alpha^{-3}) \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^{-1} \right] \cos \theta \quad (21)$$

In agreement with paradoxes implying no force on the cylinder for the classical infinite fluid, this relationship predicts that pressure differences within the fluid become vanishingly small as A increases towards infinity (while r remains less or equal than A .)

4.1.2. Higher Order Terms

Higher order terms were calculated for various values of A/R using the expansion for the corresponding stream function (Table 2), with a digital computer performing the arithmetic and recordkeeping. Table 3 shows a few results, up to the square of the Reynolds number. As before, the coefficients are shown in Fortran's exponential format. Zero pressure is set at the point

$$r = A, \quad \theta = \pi/2.$$

Table 3. Coefficients p_{knji} for the Pressure, Eq. 20

$A/R=2$			$i = \text{Power of } r/R$												
k	n	j	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	0	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5
0	1	0							-8.589E+00		-2.147E+01				
1	0	0				2.113E+00		2.062E+01		-4.946E+01		8.645E+01		-9.220E+00	
1	0	1						-3.458E+01		7.607E+01		4.610E+01			
1	2	0				-3.073E+00		-6.430E+01		1.521E+02		-8.069E+01			
1	2	1						6.915E+01				-9.220E+01			
2	1	0	2.337E-01		3.257E+01			3.874E+02		-4.842E+02		5.549E+01		8.705E+00	-2.200E-01
2	1	1			-1.856E+01			-4.198E+02		-5.380E+02		2.128E+02		1.650E+00	
2	1	2						6.187E+01		-5.568E+01		1.237E+02			
2	1	3								-5.156E+01					
2	3	0	-2.887E-01		-4.498E+01			-4.701E+02		7.004E+02		-1.972E+02		1.205E+01	
2	3	1			2.475E+01			5.230E+02		5.321E+02		-3.019E+02		-2.200E+00	
2	3	2						-6.187E+01		1.547E+02		-2.475E+02			
$A/R=4$															
0	1	0							-4.669E-01		-3.969E+00				
1	0	0				6.245E-03		4.184E-01		-9.077E-01		2.599E+00		-4.360E-01	
1	0	1						-3.474E-01		2.187E+00		1.853E+00			
1	2	0				-9.083E-03		-1.068E+00		4.374E+00		-1.492E+00			
1	2	1						6.949E-01				-3.706E+00			
2	1	0	3.755E-05		2.632E-02			1.563E+00		-1.914E+00		1.093E+00		-1.025E+00	1.395E-01
2	1	1			-1.014E-02			-1.116E+00		-3.128E+00		1.129E+00		-8.894E-01	
2	1	2						1.149E-01		-1.115E-01		9.193E-01			
2	1	3								-3.256E-01					
2	3	0	-4.639E-05		-3.594E-02			-2.000E+00		2.425E+00		-1.304E+00		8.897E-01	
2	3	1			1.352E-02			1.401E+00		3.697E+00		-1.339E+00		1.186E+00	
2	3	2						-1.149E-01		9.767E-01		-1.839E+00			
$A/R=10$															
0	1	0							-2.995E-02		-1.512E+00				
1	0	0				2.569E-05		1.868E-02		-1.748E-01		-1.044E-01		-7.007E-02	
1	0	1						-8.493E-03		2.915E-01		2.831E-01			
1	2	0				-3.737E-05		-4.302E-02		5.831E-01		7.749E-01			
1	2	1						1.699E-02				-5.662E-01			
2	1	0	9.910E-09		6.461E-05			3.525E-02		-1.617E-01		1.029E-01		-4.132E-01	5.351E-02
2	1	1			-1.590E-05			-1.650E-02		-7.943E-02		5.563E-02		-3.243E-01	
2	1	2						1.070E-03		-1.065E-03		5.352E-02			
2	1	3								-1.802E-02					
2	3	0	-1.224E-08		-8.747E-05			-4.683E-02		-2.161E-02		-2.325E-01		3.101E-01	
2	3	1			2.120E-05			2.113E-02		2.141E-01		-5.774E-02		4.324E-01	
2	3	2						-1.070E-03		5.405E-02		-1.070E-01			

Table 3 (cont'd)

<i>A/R=100</i>			<i>i = Power of r/R</i>												
<i>k</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>j</i>	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	0	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5
0	1	0							-1.109E-04		-5.547E-01				
1	0	0				3.525E-10		5.637E-05		-6.756E-02		-4.847E-01		-9.614E-03	
1	0	1						-1.154E-05		3.847E-02		3.846E-02			
1	2	0				-5.128E-10		-1.204E-04		7.695E-02		1.046E+00			
1	2	1						2.308E-05				-7.692E-02			
2	1	0	5.037E-16		6.471E-10		6.960E-05		-9.642E-02		-8.665E+00		-1.708E-01		1.897E-02
2	1	1			-8.000E-11		-1.679E-05		2.862E-02		2.668E-03		-1.138E-01		
2	1	2					5.334E-07		-5.334E-07		2.667E-03				
2	1	3							-8.891E-04						
2	3	0	-6.222E-16		-8.695E-10		-9.490E-05		-3.522E-02		-7.592E-02		1.397E-01		
2	3	1			1.067E-10		2.194E-05		1.067E-02		-2.669E-03		1.518E-01		
2	3	2					-5.334E-07		2.667E-03		-5.334E-03				
<i>A/R=1000</i>															
0	1	0							-6.771E-07		-3.385E-01				
1	0	0				1.313E-14		3.255E-07		-4.172E-02		-5.107E-01		-3.581E-03	
1	0	1						-4.298E-08		1.433E-02		1.433E-02			
1	2	0				-1.910E-14		-6.796E-07		2.865E-02		1.050E+00			
1	2	1						8.596E-08				-2.865E-02			
2	1	0	1.145E-22		2.204E-14		3.571E-07		-9.194E-02		-3.729E+02		-1.069E-01		1.130E-02
2	1	1			-1.819E-15		-5.772E-08		2.047E-02		6.062E-04		-6.779E-02		
2	1	2					1.212E-09		-1.212E-09		6.062E-04				
2	1	3							-2.021E-04						
2	3	0	-1.415E-22		-2.954E-14		-4.903E-07		-2.199E-02		-4.519E-02		8.990E-02		
2	3	1			2.425E-15		7.595E-08		2.425E-03		-6.062E-04		9.038E-02		
2	3	2					-1.212E-09		6.062E-04		-1.212E-03				

5. Drag

Forces on the cylinder are classified [1] as form drag (derived from pressure) and friction drag (derived from shear stress), and are commonly expressed in terms of “drag coefficients” using L as the cylinder length and $2RL$ as the cross-sectional area facing the flow:

$$\text{Drag Coefficient} = C_D = \frac{\text{Drag Force}}{\frac{1}{2}\rho V^2 \times 2RL} \quad (22)$$

Direct application of the techniques described by Bird, Stewart and Lightfoot [1] yield the following with the stream function and flow properties presented above:

$$C_{D,Form} = -\frac{4}{\text{Re}} \int_0^\pi \frac{\mathcal{P}R}{\mu V} \Big|_{r=R} \cos \theta \, d\theta \quad (23)$$

$$C_{D,Friction} = -\frac{4}{\text{Re}} \int_0^\pi \frac{\partial^2(\psi/VR)}{\partial(r/R)^2} \Big|_{r=R} \sin \theta \, d\theta \quad (24)$$

5.1. Results

5.1.1. Creeping Flow

Equations 21 for pressure and 17 for the stream function yield with equations 23 and 24 the drag coefficient for creeping flow as:

$$C_{D0,Form} = \frac{4\pi}{\Delta_0 \text{Re}} [1 + \alpha^{-1} + 3\alpha^{-2} + 3\alpha^{-3}] \quad (25)$$

$$C_{D0,Friction} = \frac{4\pi}{\Delta_0 \text{Re}} (1 - \alpha^{-1})(1 + \alpha^{-1})^2 \quad (26)$$

$$C_{D0,Total} = \frac{8\pi}{\Delta_0 \text{Re}} [1 + \alpha^{-1} + \alpha^{-2} + \alpha^{-3}] \quad (27)$$

where:

$$\alpha = \frac{A}{R} \quad (16)$$

$$\Delta_0 = (1 + \alpha^{-1} + \alpha^{-2} + \alpha^{-3}) \ln \alpha - (1 - \alpha^{-1})(1 + 2\alpha^{-1} + \alpha^{-2}) \quad (18)$$

It should be noted that all three formulas predict that the drag would vanish for creeping flow with an infinite fluid. The principal factor is the logarithm of α in Δ_0 in the denominator.

5.1.2. Higher Order Terms

Table 4 presents results for the drag coefficient for various values of the parameter A/R in the form of coefficients for the expression:

$$C_D = \frac{1}{\text{Re}} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} c_k \left(\frac{\text{Re}}{2}\right)^k \quad (28)$$

Only even powers k contribute to the drag in this expansion. Again, Fortran's exponential format is used in the presentation.

Table 4. Coefficients c_k for the Drag Coefficient, Eq. 28

$A/R=2$	$k = \text{Power of } (Re/2)$						
Type	0	2	4	6	8	10	12
Form	1.889E+02	4.710E-01	-9.594E-04	2.197E-06	2.152E-09	-1.000E-10	1.447E-12
Friction	8.095E+01	7.328E-02	-1.507E-04	2.256E-07	1.509E-09	-2.678E-11	3.844E-13
Total	2.698E+02	5.443E-01	-1.110E-03	2.423E-06	3.661E-09	-1.268E-10	1.831E-12
$A/R=4$							
Form	2.787E+01	8.547E-01	-3.524E-02	2.375E-03	-1.918E-04	1.807E-05	-1.990E-06
Friction	2.200E+01	3.308E-01	-1.416E-02	8.847E-04	-6.569E-05	5.729E-06	-5.952E-07
Total	4.987E+01	1.186E+00	-4.940E-02	3.260E-03	-2.575E-04	2.380E-05	-2.585E-06
$A/R=10$							
Form	9.691E+00	2.365E+00	-1.142E+00	8.493E-01	-7.095E-01	6.242E-01	-5.646E-01
Friction	9.315E+00	1.640E+00	-8.272E-01	5.995E-01	-4.877E-01	4.196E-01	-3.728E-01
Total	1.901E+01	4.005E+00	-1.969E+00	1.449E+00	-1.197E+00	1.044E+00	-9.374E-01
$A/R=100$							
Form	3.486E+00	5.587E+01	-3.533E+03	3.155E+05	-3.058E+07	3.046E+09	-3.064E+11
Friction	3.485E+00	5.491E+01	-3.504E+03	3.127E+05	-3.029E+07	3.016E+09	-3.032E+11
Total	6.971E+00	1.108E+02	-7.036E+03	6.282E+05	-6.087E+07	6.062E+09	-6.096E+11
$A/R=1000$							
Form	2.127E+00	2.344E+03	-1.635E+07	1.540E+11	-1.562E+15	1.621E+19	-1.695E+23
Friction	2.127E+00	2.343E+03	-1.635E+07	1.540E+11	-1.562E+15	1.621E+19	-1.695E+23
Total	4.254E+00	4.687E+03	-3.269E+07	3.081E+11	-3.123E+15	3.242E+19	-3.390E+23

5.2. Discussion

This series solution, although complete, does have limitations. As with the stream function, the drag coefficient does not converge at high fluid velocities. Some estimates can be made from Table 4 on the region of convergence by comparing consecutive coefficients (of these of alternating signs) to determine the Reynolds number when the series would cease to converge.

Some valid conclusions can be drawn though: The drag on the cylinder decreases as the parameter A increases. It is reasonable that increasing the quantity of unrestrained fluid surrounding the solid would decrease the effect on the solid. The lower drag is related to smaller velocity gradients, which in turn make the disturbances created by the solid cylinder extend farther into the fluid.

The prediction that the drag would decrease and eventually vanish when A increases indefinitely, is somewhat surprising, but agrees with the "paradoxes" in the literature. The latter, often derived with approximations involving an ideal fluid, highlight the improbable situation of a solid (the cylinder) immersed in a moving fluid that exerts no force on the solid. On the other hand, were the drag coefficient be non-zero the total lateral force on the cylinder would be infinite (infinite cylinder in an infinite fluid), reaction that would have to be opposed somehow by the distant fluid.

According to this solution, as A increases the decrease in drag is very gradual, being inversely proportional to the logarithm of (A/R) for creeping flow. Considering creeping flow in Table 4, the drag coefficient (total) for $A/R=10$ is comparable to that of a solid sphere in an infinite fluid. This drag coefficient decreases to one-third at $A/R=100$ and to one-fifth at $A/R=1000$. The effect is so gradual that experiments may have difficulty in its detection or in interpretation of any results.

6. Dedication

This work is dedicated to my wife Kim.

7. References

1. R.B. Bird, W.E. Stewart, and E.N. Lightfoot, *Transport Phenomena*, John Wiley & Sons, Inc. (1960)
2. J.M. Larrain, "Motion of fluid around a solid sphere", preprint (2021). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5525411>
3. G.K. Batchelor, *An Introduction to Fluid Dynamics*, Cambridge University Press (1967).
4. W.T. Shaw, "A simple resolution of Stokes' paradox?" arXiv:0901.3621 (2018).
5. P.Y. Lagree, "Small Re flows, $\varepsilon = \text{Re} \ll 1$ ", <http://www.lmm.jussieu.fr/~lagree/COURS/M2MHP/petitRe.pdf> (2013).
6. J.M. Larrain and C.F. Bonilla, "Theoretical analysis of pressure drop in the laminar flow of fluid in a coiled pipe", *Trans. Soc. Rheology* 14 (2), 135-47 (1970).
7. GNU Fortran compiler, part of the GNU Compiler Collection (<http://gcc.gnu.org/>), downloaded 11-30-2020, installed through the MinGW (Minimalist GNU for Windows) port (<https://sourceforge.net/projects/mingw-w64>).
8. D.H. Bailey, *MPFUN2020: A new thread-safe arbitrary precision package*, <http://www.davidhbailey.com/dhbpapers/mpfun2020.pdf>, downloaded 04-02-2021.